

STUDY OF ELECTROMAGNETIC SHIELD EFFECT OF THE METAL-PLATED CARBON FIBER COMPOSITE

Mee-Hye Oh*, Yeo-Seong Yoon, Namil Kim, Ki-Hoon Kim, Ah-Yeong Kim
 Environmental Materials and Component R&D Center, Korea Automotive Technology Institute,
 Cheonan, Chungnam 330-912, South Korea

* Corresponding author (mhoh@katech.re.kr)

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1 General Introduction

Recent, electromagnetic shielding of electrical and electronic equipment is a very important issue. Polymer composite materials to be applied in order to improve fuel economy have a sensitive problem about the electromagnetic shielding effectiveness. In particular, the development of electric vehicles increased electronic components. Electronic components are required the electrical conductivity and thermal conductivity depending on the parts. Material of various functions is required. Making materials, molding and mechanical properties that meet needs while satisfying While need properties are satisfied, should be made optimized composite recipe. For example molding and mechanical properties so on. In this study, when made of CF composite, it would be maximized electromagnetic shield effect. We should made of metal coated carbon fiber reinforced PA matrix composite.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

Tenax carbon fiber was used, the surface of the metal coating of the nickel electroless plating was performed. PA composite materials were fabricated by electroless plating using a metal-coated carbon fiber as reinforcement.

Figure 1. Electroless metal coating system.

2.2 Analysis

The mechanical properties were measured using a Tinius Oslen's UTM. Thermal conductivity (Anter Co) by 2inch disc specimens were measured at room temperature using a potentiostat IVIUM's electrical conductivity was measured.

3 Result & discussion

CF reinforced composite compared to GF reinforced composite showed a weight reduction of approximately 30%. Thermal conductivity has been improved about 30% compared to other 30~40% filler composite.

Figure 2. Metal coated Carbon fiber composite

Table 1. Properties of metal coated CF composite

Properties		Value
Mechanical	TS (MPa)	99
	FM (MPa)	10,200
	Elongation (%)	0.45
Thermal conductivity	W/mK @ 30°C	0.37
Electrical conductivity	Ω/cm^2	0.04
Gravity		1.3

In particular, the electrical conductivity was $0.04 \Omega/\text{cm}^2$. It is related to the deep electrical conductivity and electromagnetic shielding. In general, the higher electrical conductivity of the composite material, the electromagnetic shielding value is improved. It was reported that shielding effectiveness could be improved more than 10 times when electric conductivity of shielding materials is above $20\text{S}/\text{cm}$.

But Depending on the filler content of composite materials is trade off between functionality and molding properties.

4 Conclusion

As a result, lightweight composite material of the electronics housing should have the electromagnetic shielding performance. CF composite material by the metal coating in order to enhance the electrical conductivity has increased electrical conductivity. Electromagnetic shielding and electrical conductivity performance is improved with the thermal conductivity.